

Active, Passive, and Absorptive RIS-Aided 6G Network Under Non-Orthogonal CCI

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ABSTRACT This paper investigates the impact of randomly deployed non-orthogonal co-channel interference (CCI), originating from the information exchange process among non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) users, in an active, passive, and absorptive reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS)-assisted dual-hop network. More specifically, the study considers that the information exchange process involves the source utilizing active, passive, or absorptive RIS architecture, along with a line of sight (LOS)/non-line of sight (NLOS) link between source and destination terminals. Additionally, this study considers the limited non-orthogonal CCI affecting the destination terminal in an independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) non-orthogonal CCI scenario. Theoretical insights and Monte Carlo-based simulations collectively demonstrate that non-orthogonal CCI severely degrades system performance, particularly in high signal-to-noise ratio conditions, leading to notable losses in system coding gain. Meanwhile, results also reveal that increasing the number of RIS elements stabilizes the system and mitigates the impact of CCI on its performance.

INDEX TERMS Reconfigurable intelligent surface, active, passive, absorptive, co-channel interference, performance analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

As millimeter and terahertz-waves are susceptible to fading between building blocks, the reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) architecture has emerged as an essential component for improving wireless propagation in sixth-generation (6G) wireless mobile communications [1], [2]. The evolution initiated by passive RISs [1] is now advancing with the introduction of active [3], [4], [5], hybrid [6], [7], absorptive [8], distributed, zero-energy [9], and simultaneous transmission and reflection (STAR)-RIS paradigms [10]. RIS technology distinguishes itself from traditional relaying by providing notable advantages in spectrum and energy efficiency. Unlike

relays, passive RIS units solely reflect received signals without processing, differentiating them from relay modes, such as half-duplex (HD) [11] and full-duplex (FD) [12]. Notably, relay operating modes still contend with challenges like the pre-log factor and loop-interference drawbacks [13]. In recent years, active RIS has also received great attention due to its capability to amplify the incident signal and reflect to other direction [3], [5], [14], [15]. Meanwhile, academic and industrial stakeholders in the telecom domain are expecting a dramatic increase in the number of mobile terminals [16]. This trend is anticipated to increase co-channel interference (CCI) occurrences in the near future. Prominent examples

include leakage interference from beamforming side lobes and information exchange among non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) users [17].¹

Thereby, some of the studies in the literature scrutinize this issue and investigate the detrimental effects of CCI on RIS-assisted systems. The study in [18] investigates the system outage performance of a multiple decode-and-forward (DF)-based HD relay-assisted communication under Rayleigh fading. In addition, [18] considers that the source terminal has N reflecting elements and relay-destination terminals experience CCI. Moreover, [18] presents an opportunistic relay selection strategy to minimize the system outage performance and overhead. The authors in [19] consider a wireless network with a RIS-assisted source, which has N_1 reflecting elements, communicating with a destination via K RIS-assisted multiple HD-DF relay nodes, having N_2 reflecting units. Furthermore, [19] considers that relay and destination terminals are affected by an arbitrary number of CCI terminals under Rayleigh fading conditions. Meanwhile, opportunistic relay selection is adopted in [19], which is based on succeeded the decoding received signal. Finally, results reveal that the proposed selection algorithm achieves increased cooperative diversity order and the interference at the destination is more detrimental than the interference at the relay terminal on the system outage performance. The paper in [20] investigates the constructive interference effects on a downlink network, where a multi-antenna base station (BS) communicates with K mobile terminals via a RIS with M reflecting elements. To enhance the system's error-rate performance, optimization techniques are employed to redesign the phase shifts at the RIS unit, also utilizing a greedy algorithm to minimize the error floors at medium-to-high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Then, the work in [21] investigates the CCI effects on the outage and bit error rate (BER) performance of RIS and DF-based HD relay-assisted mixed free-space optical communication and radio frequency systems. In addition, the authors assume that the destination terminal is affected by a limited number of CCI terminals subject to Rayleigh fading conditions. Here, the direct-link between source and destination terminals does not exist due to excessive fading and path-loss.

Reference [22] investigates the system performance of RIS-assisted wireless powered interference-limited networks. In greater detail, the destination terminal is affected by a limited number of CCI and the direct-link between source and destination terminals does not exist. Meanwhile the authors assume Generalized- K and Nakagami- m fading environments for the RIS and interference links, respectively. The study in [23] focuses on a topology where the source communicates with the destination through a RIS unit, which has N reflecting unit, under Rayleigh fading conditions. At the same time,

the paper does not consider a direct-link between the source and destination and communication is established only via the RIS unit. Moreover, [23] considers that the destination terminal is affected by a limited number of independent, equally powered CCIs. Since the aforementioned system operates in interference-limited regime, [23] neglects the thermal noise effects over the system performance. [23] investigates the system performance by means of outage probability, error probability, and average channel capacity. [23] also provides asymptotic analysis to get more insight of the derived analytical results. In addition, [23] utilizes binary phase shift keying and differential phase shift keying modulations to investigate the system BER performance. Moreover, [23] also takes into consideration the ideal and practical phase shift effects on the system outage performance in the presence of CCI. [23] investigates the effects of the different numbers and powers of interferers and also different numbers of reflecting unit effects on the system performance. Next, the work in [24] investigates the outage and average bit error rate performance of single and multiple RIS-assisted dual-hop networks without a direct-link. The presented analysis and performance evaluation consider that the destination terminal is affected by a limited number of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) CCI subject to Rayleigh fading. Additionally, a best RIS selection algorithm for the multiple RIS-assisted system is presented, enhancing the network's reliability.

The authors in [25] shed light on how CCI, which is caused by active uplink transmissions, can be minimized by using RISs in the RIS-aided FD networks. The authors consider two scenarios, with and without direct-link, and adopt various optimization techniques. Results reveal that a larger RIS is required for efficient CCI cancellation. Another work investigates the outage and achievable-rate performance of passive RIS-aided dual-hop network [26]. The investigation considers that source and destination terminals do not have a direct-link and all information exchange is completed via passive RIS and destination terminal is affected by a limited number of CCI. The paper in [27] investigates the CCI effects on the RIS-aided multiple-input single output wireless communication system. Here the outage probability, bit-error rate, and ergodic capacity performance metrics are analyzed. The study in [28] investigates the performance of RIS-aided FD network. The authors assume that users and RIS terminal are affected by CCI and because of the FD information exchange process, user terminals suffer from the self-interference that is caused by transmitting and receiving at the same time. In this setting, the authors focus on the analysis of the outage and ergodic capacity performance of the RIS-aided FD network. Furthermore, the authors in [29] study a network where mobile terminals introduce CCI on a passive RIS-aided dual-hop network. More specifically, it is considered that the destination terminal is affected by a limited number of mobile CCI terminals. The obtained results reveal that mobile CCI has severe effects on the system performance compared to static CCI. Then, the study in [30] investigates the performance of RIS-aided systems in the presence of interference. Aiming to reduce phase adjustment overheads, the

¹It is worth noting that while practical RIS implementations often encounter significant interference from quantization lobes due to discrete phase shifts, our focus remains on analyzing the CCI arising from the information exchange among NOMA users. Expanding the scope to include multi-antenna interference sources and the impact of RIS quantization lobes would undoubtedly enrich the analysis; however, such considerations are left for future work.

authors adopt quasi-static phase shifting where the phase shifts do not vary with the instantaneous channel state information (CSI), offering an attractive performance-complexity trade-off. Vega-Sánchez et al. [31] investigates the achievable secrecy performance of RIS-aided dual-hop network in the presence of a single eavesdropper. The investigation also considers that RIS terminal is affected by electromagnetic interference. The work in [32] focuses on the performance of RIS-aided downlink power-domain NOMA in Nakagami- m fading channels with CCI. Considering the Gamma approximation, they provide closed-form expressions for the ergodic capacity and outage probability, under the impact of CCI. Moreover, Monte Carlo simulations are presented highlighting that RIS-NOMA outperforms RIS-OMA for varying numbers of users and reflecting elements.

Finally, the authors in [33] investigate the performance of passive RIS-aided downlink two-users NOMA network. The investigation considers that BS has an access to user one via IRS terminal while it has a direct access to user two. The investigation also considers that two NOMA users are affected by a limited number of CCI. Likewise, [34] investigates the outage performance of passive and absorptive RIS-aided uplink NOMA networks in the presence of CCI affecting the BS. The literature comparison table is presented in Table I.

Aiming to build on prior works in RIS-aided NOMA networks, in this study, we investigate the impact of randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI, introduced from NOMA communication between different users, in a dual-hop RIS-aided network. Furthermore, we analyzed the performance under three different RIS modes, i.e. active, passive, and absorptive. While prior studies have analyzed RIS-assisted systems under generalized fading and hardware impairments [35], [36], [37], [38], these works typically address specific fading environments or hardware limitations in isolation, without jointly considering the interplay between RIS operation modes and non-orthogonal CCI. In contrast, our study develops a unified analytical framework comparing active, passive, and absorptive RIS operation under randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI, a realistic and practically motivated interference scenario that has not been jointly addressed in the RIS literature. More specifically, this work provides the following contributions:

- Aiming to provide a generalized view on RIS-aided networks, we include in our study three different RIS operation modes. The first mode corresponds to N reflecting element equipped active RIS, with power amplifiers and no signal processing capabilities, then, we present an analysis on passive RISs, and finally we present results for absorptive-RISs, the wireless topology we focus herein consists of a line-of-sight (LOS)/direct-link and non-LOS (NLOS), between source and destination. To cater for real-world impairments, we assume that the destination is affected by a limited number of randomly deployed i.i.d. non-orthogonal CCI subject to Rayleigh fading. Differently from [23], instead of constant transmit power, the investigation in this paper considers proportional transmit power associated with source

FIGURE 1. Active, passive, and absorptive RIS-assisted dual-hop network in the presence of non-orthogonal CCI.

terminal's transmit power and Euclidean distance for the interference.

- For this topology, we provide a thorough theoretical analysis, in terms of outage probability (OP), error probability (EP), throughput, energy and spectral efficiency. Analytical and asymptotic derivations regarding the aforementioned performance metrics are provided and verified by means of Monte-Carlo based intensive computer simulations.

The remaining parts of the investigation are as follows: Section II provides detailed descriptions regarding the investigated system model along with channel statistics. Section III presents the analytical and asymptotic derivations of performance metrics. Then, Section IV presents the numerical result, and finally Section V concludes the investigation. The list of acronyms and Notations are presented in Tables I and III, respectively.

Notations: Throughout the paper, the superscripts “a”, “p”, and “abs” denote the operating modes of active, passive, and absorptive RIS, respectively. The $F_h(\cdot)$ represents the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a random variable (RV) h . The $f_h(\cdot)$ term represents the probability density function (PDF) of a random variable h . $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function [39, Eq. (8.310.1)]. $\gamma(a, b)$ is the lower incomplete Gamma function [39, Eq. (8.350.1)] and $\Gamma(a, b)$ is the upper incomplete Gamma function [39, Eq. (8.350.2¹¹)]. $B(x, y)$ is the Beta function [39, Eq. (8.384.1)]. $(a)_n$ is the Pochhammer symbol [39] and $\binom{x}{y}$ is the Binomial coefficient [39]. All log are base 2 unless stated otherwise. The operator $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ stands for expectation, while $\Pr(\cdot)$ represents probability. $G_{p,q}^{m,n}[\cdot]$ is the Meijer's G-Function [39, Eq. (9.301)]. ${}_pF_q(a_1, \dots, a_p; b_1, \dots, b_q; x)$ is the generalized hypergeometric function [39, Eq. (9.14)]. The $\mathcal{CN}(\mu, \sigma^2)$ is complex Gaussian RV with mean of μ and variance of σ^2 .

II. SYSTEM MODEL & CHANNEL STATISTICS

Fig. 1 present a RIS-aided network, under non-orthogonal CCI, where three different operation modes are adopted, i.e.

TABLE 1. Comparison of Existing Works and This Study

Reference	RIS Mode	Channel Model	CCI Consideration	Performance Metrics	Key Contribution
[4]	Active and Passive	Rayleigh and NLOS	No	Sum-Rate	Performance comparison of active and passive RISs and sum-rate maximization for active RIS-aided systems.
[5]	Active and Passive	Rayleigh and NLOS	No	Achievable rate	Performance comparison of active and passive RIS under the same power budget and optimal power splitting strategy for active RIS.
[6]	Active and Passive	Rayleigh and LOS	No	Achievable rate	Performance comparison of active and passive RISs under the same power budget and reflection coefficient optimization.
[7]	Primarily Passive, with discussions on hybrid active-passive integration	Rayleigh and Rician	Addressed (CCI management)	Achievable rate, power scaling, and reflection optimization	Tutorial on RIS-aided systems, presenting reflection optimization, channel estimation and hybrid architectures.
[8]	Active, Passive, and Hybrid	Rayleigh and Rician	No	Not explicitly evaluated	Overview of RIS technologies, including passive, active and hybrid architectures, potential applications and challenges.
[9]	Passive and Absorptive	Rayleigh and LOS	Yes (jamming interference)	Absorption level and normalized total transmit power	Analysis of the impact of absorptive RISs for interference mitigation in uplink NOMA with smart jammers.
[18]	Relay	Rayleigh	Yes (Non-orthogonal CCI)	Outage, error, throughput, spectral and energy efficiency	Performance Analysis of relay-aided system under non-orthogonal CCI.
[19]	Passive	Rayleigh	Yes (CCI at relay and destination)	Outage probability	Performance analysis of RIS-based relay-aided communication.
[20]	Passive	Rayleigh	Yes (CCI at relay and destination)	Outage probability	Performance analysis of RIS-aided multi-hop relay networks.
[21]	Passive	Rayleigh	No (constructive interference)	BER	Phase shift optimization for RIS-aided wireless networks.
[22]	Passive	Mixed FSO-RF	Yes (CCI at destination)	Outage probability, BER	Performance analysis of RIS-aided DF relaying for hybrid networks.
[23]	Passive	Rayleigh	Yes (CCI at destination)	Outage probability, throughput, error	Performance analysis of RIS and relay-aided systems in the presence of CCI.
[24]	Passive	Rayleigh and NLOS	Yes (CCI at destination)	Outage probability, average BER, average capacity	Performance analysis of RIS-aided networks with CCI.
[25]	Passive	Rayleigh and NLOS	Yes (CCI at destination)	Outage probability, BER	Performance analysis of multiple RIS-aided network under CCI.
[26]	Passive	Rayleigh, LOS and NLOS	Yes (CCI in RIS-aided networks)	CCI level, downlink rate	Performance analysis of RIS-aided networks with CCI.
[27]	Passive	Rayleigh and NLOS	Yes (CCI at destination)	Outage probability and capacity	Performance of RIS-aided wireless network under CCI.
[28]	Passive	Rayleigh and Rician	Yes (CCI at destination)	Outage probability, BER, rate	Performance analysis of RIS-aided wireless network in the presence of CCI.
[29]	Passive	Weibull	Yes (CCI at Source, RIS, and Destination))	Outage probability, ergodic capacity	Performance analysis of RIS-aided systems with CCI.
[30]	Passive	Rayleigh (NLOS)	Yes (Mobile CCI)	Outage probability, error, rate	Performance analysis of RIS-aided multi-user networks with CCI.
[31]	Passive	Rayleigh and Rician	Yes (CCI at mobile users)	Ergodic rate	Effect of co-channel interference in IRS-assisted communication.
[32]	Passive	Gamma and Exponential (LOS)	Yes (Electromagnetic CCI at RIS)	Secrecy outage probability	Secrecy performance analysis of RIS-aided systems under electromagnetic CCI.
[33]	Passive	Nakagami- m (NLOS)	Yes (CCI at NOMA users)	Ergodic capacity, outage probability	Performance analysis of RIS-aided NOMA with CCI.
[34]	Passive	Rayleigh	Yes (CCI at NOMA users)	Outage probability, ergodic rate	Performance analysis of RIS-aided downlink power-domain NOMA systems.
[35] This Work	Passive, Absorptive Active, Passive, Absorptive	Rayleigh Rayleigh, Gamma	Yes (CCI at BS) Yes (Randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI)	Outage probability Outage probability, error probability, throughput, energy and spectral efficiency	On the performance of RIS-assisted uplink NOMA. Impact of RIS Modes (Active, Passive, Absorptive) under randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI affecting the BS.

TABLE 2. List of Acronyms

5G	Fifth-generation
6G	Sixth-generation
AWGN	Additive white Gaussian noise
a	Active RIS
a+d	Active RIS with direct-link
abs	Absorptive RIS
abs+d	Absorptive RIS with direct-link
BER	Bit error rate
BPSK	Binary phase-shift keying
BS	Base-station
CCI	Co-channel Interference
CDF	Cumulative distribution function
DF	Decode-and-forward
EE	Energy efficiency
FD	Full-duplex
HD	Half-duplex
Hz	Hertz
i.i.d.	Independent and identically distributed
LOS	Line of sight
MIMO	Multiple-input multiple-output
MT	Mobile terminal
NOMA	Non-orthogonal multiple access
NLOS	Non-line of sight
OMA	Orthogonal multiple access
p	Passive RIS
p+d	Passive RIS with direct-link
PDF	Probability density function
RV	Random variable
RIS	Reconfigurable intelligent surface
SE	Spectral efficiency
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
SINR	Signal-to-interference plus noise ratio
STAR	Simultaneous transmission and reflection
QPSK	Quadrature phase-shift keying

active RIS with power amplifiers, without signal processing capabilities, passive RIS, and absorptive RIS. Moreover, a single antenna equipped mobile terminal (MT) makes information exchange with a single antenna equipped destination, which is BS, via RIS with NLOS and RIS with LOS/direct-link between source.

In this study, we assume a single-antenna BS to analyze the fundamental impact of RIS operational modes in a NOMA-based network. While modern 5G and 6G networks frequently employ massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO), the single-antenna BS model remains relevant in scenarios such as low-power edge nodes, small cells, and Internet of Things (IoT) applications, where large antenna arrays may not be feasible. Additionally, this assumption allows for analytical tractability and closed-form performance derivations without excessive complexity [40].

It is worth noting that while practical RIS implementations may introduce additional factors such as scatterers, beamforming side lobes, quantization lobes, and energy losses, our study adopts an idealized model to focus on the

TABLE 3. List of Notations

ϕ_i	Adjustable phase at i th reflecting element
ρ	Amplification factor of active RIS
B	Bandwidth
h_i	Channel impulse response MT \rightarrow RIS
g_i	Channel impulse response RIS \rightarrow BS
f	Channel impulse response MT \rightarrow BS
m_j	Channel impulse response j th CCI \rightarrow BS
$\mathcal{CN}(\mu, \sigma^2)$	Complex Gaussian with mean of μ and variance of σ^2
ρ_i	Energy coefficient of i th reflecting element
$d_{\text{MT-RIS}}$	Euclidean distance MT \rightarrow RIS
$d_{\text{RIS-BS}}$	Euclidean distance RIS \rightarrow BS
$d_{\text{MT-BS}}$	Euclidean distance MT \rightarrow BS
$d_{m_j\text{-BS}}$	Euclidean distance j th CCI \rightarrow BS
$d_{m_M\text{-BS}}$	Euclidean distance M th CCI \rightarrow BS
$\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$	Expectation operator
Ω_{h_i}	Mean of $ h_i ^2$
Ω_{g_i}	Mean of $ g_i ^2$
Ω_f	Mean of $ f ^2$
Ω_{m_j}	Mean of $ m_j ^2$
n_i	Noise term from the amplifier at i th reflecting element
N	Number of reflecting elements at RIS
M	Number of CCIs at BS
ν	Path-loss exponent
Θ	Phase shifting matrix
x	Transmit information of MT
a_j	Transmit information of j th CCI
R_{th}	Target rate
γ_{th}	Target threshold rate
τ	Throughput
w_n	Thermal noise
$\sigma_{h_i}^2$	Variance of $ h_i ^2$
$\sigma_{g_i}^2$	Variance of $ g_i ^2$
σ_f^2	Variance of $ f ^2$
$\sigma_{m_j}^2$	Variance of $ m_j ^2$
$\sigma_{n_i}^2$	Variance of noise at i th reflecting element
$\sigma_{w_n}^2$	Variance of AWGN
P_s	MT's transmit power
P_j	j th CCI's transmit power
α_j	j th CCI's amplification coefficient
α_M	M th CCI's amplification coefficient

fundamental performance impact of active, passive, and absorptive RIS modes in a NOMA-based communication system. This approach is widely used in analytical studies to derive closed-form expressions and fundamental insights [41], [42]. The energy reflection coefficient of RIS elements is assumed to be 1 in passive mode, following conventional models that establish theoretical performance limits before incorporating practical impairments [42]. While losses due to hardware constraints and multiplicative fading are valid concerns, analyzing them in detail would significantly increase model complexity and require numerical evaluations, which fall outside the scope of this work. However, extending this

analysis to include such impairments could be an interesting direction for future research [43], [44].

The RV $h_i, \forall_i = 1, \dots, N$, represents the channel impulse response between MT \rightarrow RIS. h_i is a complex Gaussian RV with zero mean and $\sigma_{h_i}^2 d_{\text{MT-RIS}}^{-\nu}$ variance. i.e. $h_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{h_i}^2 d_{\text{MT-RIS}}^{-\nu})$, where $d_{\text{MT-RIS}}$ is the distance between MT \rightarrow RIS and ν is the pathloss exponent and takes values between 2 – 6 [45]. $g_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{g_i}^2 d_{\text{RIS-BS}}^{-\nu})$ is the channel impulse response RIS \rightarrow BS, where $d_{\text{RIS-BS}}$ is the distance between RIS \rightarrow BS. Next, $f \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_f^2 d_{\text{MT-BS}}^{-\nu})$ is the channel impulse response between MT and BS, where $d_{\text{MT-BS}}$ is the distance between MT \rightarrow BS. In addition, $m_j \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{m_j}^2 d_{m_j\text{-BS}}^{-\nu}), \forall_j = 1, \dots, M$, is the channel impulse response between j th CCI \rightarrow BS, where $d_{m_j\text{-BS}}$ is the distance between j th CCI \rightarrow BS. The distances, channel impulse responses, and power allocation coefficients of the CCI terminals are sorted as: $d_{m_1\text{-BS}} \leq \dots \leq d_{m_M\text{-BS}}, |m_1|^2 \geq \dots \geq |m_M|^2$, and $1 > \alpha_j \geq \dots \geq \alpha_M > 0$, where $\sum_{j=1}^M \alpha_j = 1$, respectively. The amplitudes of all channels are distributed according to Rayleigh distribution. It should be noted that the i.i.d. case is considered for modeling the CCI subject to Rayleigh fading.

According to Fig. 1, MT transmits information to the destination via active, passive, and absorptive RIS with LOS/direct-link. The received signals at BS for the active, passive, and absorptive RIS modes are written as follows:

$$y_{\text{BS}}^{\text{a+d}} = \sqrt{P_s} f x + \sqrt{P_s} \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \theta_i g_i x + \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \theta_i g_i x + \sum_{j=1}^M \sqrt{P_j \alpha_j} m_j a_j + w_n, \quad (1)$$

$$y_{\text{BS}}^{\text{p+d/abs+d}} = \sqrt{P_s} f x + \sqrt{P_s} \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \theta_i g_i x + \sum_{j=1}^M \sqrt{P_j \alpha_j} m_j a_j + w_n, \quad (2)$$

where P_s is the transmit power of MT. x is the transmit information, which has a unit variance $\mathbb{E}[|x|^2] = 1$. The n_i is the noise term from the amplifier at i th reflecting element which follows $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{n_i}^2)$. $\theta_i = \rho_i e^{j\phi_i}, \forall_i = 1, \dots, N$, and $\Theta = \text{diag}([\rho_1 e^{j\phi_1}, \dots, \rho_i e^{j\phi_i}, \dots, \rho_N e^{j\phi_N}])$ represent reflecting phase shifting matrix of RIS. The term ρ_i is the energy

coefficients of the i th element for reflecting responses. The term $\phi_i \in [0, 2\pi)$ is the adjustable phase at the i th reflected unit in the RIS. Considering $\rho_i = \rho$ [4], the Θ term can be written as: $\Theta = \rho \text{diag}([e^{j\phi_1}, \dots, e^{j\phi_i}, \dots, e^{j\phi_N}])$. In practical implementations, the phase shift ϕ_i at each RIS element is typically optimized based on CSI to enhance received signal strength. In this study, we assume an idealized continuous phase shift model, which provides an upper-bound performance analysis and allows for analytical tractability. However, in practical RIS hardware, discrete phase shifts are often employed due to quantization constraints, which can introduce additional performance losses [46]. While our model does not explicitly incorporate phase quantization, its fundamental insights remain applicable. By setting $\rho > 1$, the active mode is obtained. Conversely, by setting the term ρ to 1 and $\sigma_{n_i}^2$ to 0, the passive mode is obtained. Likewise, in absorptive mode, which neither involves an amplification process at the RIS nor amplifies noise, the term ρ takes values in the range $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$ [8], [47]. P_j is the transmit power at j th CCI. a_j , where $\mathbb{E}[|a_j|^2] = 1$, is the transmit information of the j th CCI. w_n is the thermal noise at BS and modeled as additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). Utilizing (1), the signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR) at BS is written as:

$$\gamma_{\text{BS}}^{\text{a+d}} = \frac{P_s |f| + \rho \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i| |g_i|^2}{\rho^2 \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{n_i}^2 |g_i|^2 + \sum_{j=1}^M P_j \alpha_j |m_j|^2 + \sigma_{w_n}^2} \quad (3)$$

By setting the term ρ to 1 and $\sigma_{n_i}^2$ to 0, the SINR expression for the passive and absorptive modes is obtained as:

$$\gamma_{\text{BS}}^{\text{p+d/abs+d}} = \frac{P_s |f| + \rho \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i| |g_i|^2}{\sum_{j=1}^M P_j \alpha_j |m_j|^2 + \sigma_{w_n}^2} \quad (4)$$

Note that passive and absorptive modes have the same SINR expression with a different ρ value. In passive mode, ρ term is set to 1 and in absorptive mode, ρ term is a value between $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$.

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

This section provides the analytical and asymptotic derivations of outage probability, error probability, throughput, energy and spectral efficiency performance metrics.

A. OUTAGE PROBABILITY

Below, an outage analysis is presented for the considered dual-hop RIS-aided network under the impact of non-orthogonal CCI.

$$P_{\text{out}}^{\text{a+d}}(\gamma) = \frac{1}{(\rho b)^{a+1} \Omega_f \Gamma(a+4) (\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g)^N (P_j \Omega_m)^M \Gamma(M) \Gamma(N)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s} \right)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(1+k) \Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k) \Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2) \Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2P_s \Omega_f} \right)^k \times \sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1) \Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)}{\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g} \right)^{N+u-t}} \frac{\Gamma(M+t)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_j \Omega_m} \right)^{M+t}} \quad (5)$$

Proposition 1: The OP analytical derivations are presented at the top of the next page. Note that for the case of active RIS with direct link (5) shown at the bottom of the previous page, passive RIS with direct link (6) shown at the bottom of this page, active RIS without direct link (7) shown at the bottom of this page, and passive RIS without direct link (8) shown at the bottom of this page.

Proof: See Appendix A. ■

B. ERROR PROBABILITY

With the help of [48, Eq. (27)], the CDF-based EP performance metric can be formulated as

$$\bar{P}_e = \frac{p}{2} \sqrt{\frac{q}{\pi}} \int_0^\infty \frac{\exp(-qx)}{\sqrt{x}} F(x) dx, \quad (9)$$

where $p = q = 1$ represents the binary phase shift keying (BPSK) and $p = q = 2$ represents quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) modulations.

The analytical derivations for the EP performance metric are presented in the following proposition.

Proposition 2: The EP for the proposed model is derived in the following expressions, which are presented in the middle of the next page. For the case of active RIS with direct link (10) shown at the bottom of this page, passive RIS with direct link (11) shown at the bottom of this page, active RIS without direct link (12) shown at the bottom of the next page, and passive RIS without direct link (13) shown at the bottom of the next page.

Proof: See Appendix B. ■

C. THROUGHPUT

The CDF-based throughput performance metric is formulated with the help of [49, Eq. (15(a))]:

$$\tau_{BS} = R_{th} (1 - F_{\gamma_{BS}}(\gamma_{th})) \quad (14)$$

Substituting (3) and (4) into (14), the throughput analytical expressions are obtained. Due to space limitations, the derivations are omitted and only utilized in the performance evaluation results in Section IV.

$$P_{out}^{P+d}(\gamma) = \frac{1}{(\rho b)^{a+1} \Omega_f \Gamma(a+4) \Gamma(M) (P_J \Omega_m)^M} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(1+k) \Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k) \Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2) \Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2P_s \Omega_f}\right)^k \times \sum_{u=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1) \Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+u}} \quad (6)$$

$$P_{out}^a(\gamma) = \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1) \Gamma(M) \Gamma(N) (\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g)^N (P_J \Omega_m)^M} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} \sum_{u=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1) \Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \times \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)}{\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}\right)^{N+u-t}} \frac{\Gamma(M+t)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+t}} \quad (7)$$

$$P_{out}^P(\gamma) = \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1) \Gamma(M) (P_J \Omega_m)^M} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} \sum_{u=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1) \Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+u}} \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{P}_e^{a+d} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi} (\rho b)^{a+1} \Omega_f \Gamma(a+4) P_s^{\frac{a+3}{2}} (\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g)^N (P_J \Omega_m)^M \Gamma(M) \Gamma(N)} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(1+k) \Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k) \Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2) \Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \times \left(-\frac{1}{2P_s \Omega_f}\right)^k \sum_{u=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1) \Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)}{\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}\right)^{N+u-t}} \frac{\Gamma(M+t)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+t}} \Gamma\left(\frac{a+2k+4}{2}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$\bar{P}_e^{P+d} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi} (\rho b)^{a+1} \Omega_f \Gamma(a+4) P_s^{\frac{a+3}{2}} (P_J \Omega_m)^M \Gamma(M)} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(1+k) \Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k) \Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2) \Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \left(-\frac{1}{2P_s \Omega_f}\right)^k \times \sum_{u=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1) \Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+u}} \Gamma\left(\frac{a+2k+4}{2}\right) \quad (11)$$

D. ENERGY EFFICIENCY

By definition, the energy efficiency (EE) is calculated as the system throughput over the total power consumption [50, Eq. (3)].

$$EE = \frac{\tau_{BS}}{P_s}, \tag{15}$$

E. SPECTRAL EFFICIENCY

The spectral efficiency (SE) is measured in bits/s/Hz and formulated as [51], [52].

$$SE = \frac{\tau_{BS}}{B}, \tag{16}$$

where B is the bandwidth used in the transmission.

F. ASYMPTOTIC ANALYSIS

To get additional insights from the derived analytical results, this subsection focuses on the high SNR regime. In greater detail, we evaluate the asymptotic performance for the following performance metrics:

1) OUTAGE PROBABILITY

Considering the small values of j, k terms, the asymptotic outage representations are obtained for the case of active RIS with direct link (17), passive RIS with direct link (18), active RIS without direct link (19), and passive RIS without direct link (20), all shown at the bottom of this page.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_e^a = & \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}\rho^a b^{a+1}\Gamma(a+1)(a+1)P_s^{\frac{a+1}{2}}(\sigma_n^2\Omega_g)^N(P_J\Omega_m)^M\Gamma(M)\Gamma(N)} \sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \\ & \times \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)}{(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2\Omega_g})^{N+u-t}} \frac{\Gamma(M+t)}{(\frac{1}{P_J\Omega_m})^{M+t}} \Gamma\left(\frac{a+2}{2}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$\bar{P}_e^p = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}\rho^a b^{a+1}\Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Gamma(M)(P_J\Omega_m)^M P_s^{\frac{a+1}{2}}} \sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{(\frac{1}{P_J\Omega_m})^{M+u}} \Gamma\left(\frac{a+2}{2}\right) \tag{13}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_{out}^{a+d,\infty}(\gamma) = & \frac{1}{(\rho b)^{a+1}\Omega_f\Gamma(a+4)(\sigma_n^2\Omega_g)^N(P_J\Omega_m)^M\Gamma(M)\Gamma(N)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} \\ & \times \sum_{k=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(1+k)\Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k)\Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2)\Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2P_s\Omega_f}\right)^k \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \\ & \times \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)}{(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2\Omega_g})^{N+u-t}} \frac{\Gamma(M+t)}{(\frac{1}{P_J\Omega_m})^{M+t}} \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_{out}^{p+d,\infty}(\gamma) = & \frac{1}{(\rho b)^{a+1}\Omega_f\Gamma(a+4)\Gamma(M)(P_J\Omega_m)^M} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(1+k)\Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k)\Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2)\Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2P_s\Omega_f}\right)^k \\ & \times \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{(\frac{1}{P_J\Omega_m})^{M+u}} \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_{out}^{a,\infty}(\gamma) = & \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1}\Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Gamma(M)\Gamma(N)(\sigma_n^2\Omega_g)^N(P_J\Omega_m)^M} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \\ & \times \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)}{(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2\Omega_g})^{N+u-t}} \frac{\Gamma(M+t)}{(\frac{1}{P_J\Omega_m})^{M+t}} \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$P_{out}^{p,\infty}(\gamma) = \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1}\Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Gamma(M)(P_J\Omega_m)^M} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{(\frac{1}{P_J\Omega_m})^{M+u}} \tag{20}$$

2) ERROR PROBABILITY

Following a similar procedures as in the OP asymptotic representations, the EP asymptotic representations are also obtained. The obtained derivations are omitted, being only applied in Section IV.

3) THROUGHPUT

Considering the asymptotic OP representations and utilizing it in the throughput formula, the asymptotic throughput representation is obtained. To ensure readability, the obtained derivations are omitted, being only utilized in Section IV.

4) ENERGY EFFICIENCY

Considering the asymptotic throughput expressions and using it in the (15), the asymptotic EE representation is obtained. As for the previous two performance metrics, the derivations are omitted, being only evaluated in Section IV.

G. DIVERSITY ORDER ANALYSIS

The relation between diversity order and coding gain is expressed as [53]

$$\bar{P}_{\text{out}} = (G_c \gamma)^{-G_d}, \quad (21)$$

where G_d is the diversity order and G_c is the coding gain. Regarding the passive RIS with NLOS, its system asymptotic CDF derivation, when $P_s \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{1}{(P_j \Omega_m)^M}$, $(\frac{1}{P_j \Omega_m})^{M+u}$, and $(\frac{1}{P_s})^{\frac{a+1}{2}}$ terms approximate zero and become negligible, and γ becomes dominant. The power of γ , which is $\frac{a+1}{2}$, yields the diversity order. Note that, as it is clearly expressed in Appendix A, the a term is dependent on the number of reflecting elements. In other words, the number of reflecting elements defines the diversity order. Substituting the values of a term in Appendix A, $\frac{a+1}{2}$ is calculated as $0.8N$. The obtained result is consistent with the diversity order analysis. On the other hand, the remaining constant terms, which are presented in the following, represent the system coding gain, which is $G_c^p = \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Gamma(M)} \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})\Gamma(M+u)}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})}$.

Regarding the asymptotic performance of the active RIS with NLOS, when $P_s \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{1}{(P_j \Omega_m)^M}$, $(\frac{1}{P_j \Omega_m})^{M+t}$, and $(\frac{1}{P_s})^{\frac{a+1}{2}}$ approximate zero and become negligible, and γ becomes dominant. The power of γ , which is $\frac{a+1}{2}$, yields the diversity order. Substituting the values of a term in Appendix A section, $\frac{a+1}{2}$ is calculated as $0.8N$. The obtained result is consistent with the diversity order analysis. The remaining constant terms, which are presented below, represent the system coding gain, which is $G_c^a = \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Gamma(M)\Gamma(N)(\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g)^N} \times \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)\Gamma(M+t)}{(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g})^{N+u-t}}$.

Regarding the asymptotic performance of the passive RIS with LOS, when $P_s \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{1}{(P_j \Omega_m)^M}$, $(\frac{1}{P_j \Omega_m})^{M+t}$, $(\frac{1}{P_s})^{\frac{a+1}{2}}$, and $(-\frac{1}{2P_s \Omega_f})^{k=0}$ approximate to zero and become negligible and the γ term becomes dominant. The power of γ , which is $\frac{a+3}{2} + k$, yields the diversity order. Substituting the values of a term in Appendix A section, $\frac{a+3}{2}$ is calculated as

TABLE 4. System Configurations

Parameter	Value
Number of channel realizations	10^6
Number of CCI terminals (M)	0, 1, 2
Number of reflecting element (N)	(2,4,6,12, 30,50,60,100)
Euclidean distance MT \rightarrow RIS ($d_{\text{MT-RIS}}$)	10
Euclidean distance RIS \rightarrow BS ($d_{\text{RIS-BS}}$)	10
Euclidean distance RIS \rightarrow BS ($d_{\text{MT-BS}}$)	10
Euclidean distance j th CCI \rightarrow BS ($d_{m_j\text{-BS}}$)	1
Euclidean distance M th CCI \rightarrow BS ($d_{m_M\text{-BS}}$)	10
Path-loss exponents for the CCI	2, 3
The energy coefficient (ρ) for active RIS	1.1
The energy coefficient (ρ) for passive RIS	1
The energy coefficient (ρ) for absorptive RIS	0.5
Target rate (R_{th}), bps/Hz	10
Target threshold rate, (γ_{th}) bps/Hz	$2^{R_{\text{th}}} - 1$

$1 + 0.8N$. The obtained result is consistent with the diversity order analysis. The remaining constant terms, which are presented below represents the system coding gain, which is $G_c^{\text{p+d}} = \frac{\Gamma(a+2)}{(\rho b)^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Omega_f \Gamma(a+4)\Gamma(M)} \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+5}{2})\Gamma(M+u)}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a-2u+5}{2})}$.

Regarding the active RIS with LOS asymptotic performance, when $P_s \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{1}{(P_j \Omega_m)^M}$, $(\frac{1}{P_j \Omega_m})^{M+t}$, $(\frac{1}{P_s})^{\frac{a+1}{2}}$, and $(-\frac{1}{2P_s \Omega_f})^{k=0}$ terms approximate to zero and become negligible and γ term becomes dominant. The power of γ , which is $\frac{a+3}{2} + k$, yields the diversity order. Substituting the values of a term in Appendix A section, $\frac{a+3}{2}$ is calculated as $1 + 0.8N$. The obtained result is consistent with the diversity order analysis. The remaining constant terms, which are presented below represents the system coding gain, which is $G_c^{\text{a+d}} = \frac{\Gamma(a+2)}{(\rho b)^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Omega_f \Gamma(a+4)(\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g)^N \Gamma(M)\Gamma(N)} \times \sum_{u=0}^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a-2u+5}{2})} \sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)\Gamma(M+t)}{(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g})^{N+u-t}}$.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section validates the analytical and asymptotic derivations by means of Monte-Carlo-based computer simulations. The Matlab[®] environment is considered for the related performance analysis and 10^6 channel realizations are generated. The following parameters are considered for the system model configuration. The number of reflection unit, which is N , is set to 2, 4, 6, 12, 30, 50, 60, and 100 for different performance metrics. The number of CCI terminals, which is M , is set to 0, 1, and 2. The parameters $d_{\text{MT-RIS}}$, $d_{\text{RIS-BS}}$, and $d_{\text{MT-BS}}$ are set to 10. Since the non-orthogonal CCI terminals are randomly deployed, $d_{m_j\text{-BS}}$ is set to 1 and 10 for near and far NOMA users, respectively. Further, the v term is set to 2 and 3. The transmit power of the source terminal, which is P_s , is set to P and the transmit power of the j th interferer, which is P_j , is set to $P_j d_{m_j\text{-BS}}^{-v}$. The target rate, which is R_{th} , is set to 10 bps/Hz. The ρ term is set to 1.1, 1, and 0.5 for active, passive, and absorptive modes, respectively. The simulation parameters are also presented in Table IV. The

FIGURE 2. Outage probability analysis of Passive-RIS with NLOS and Passive-RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 4, 50, M = 0, 1, 2, \rho = 1$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

following results are obtained based on the aforementioned system configurations.

Fig. 2 presents the outage probability performance and for two cases, i.e. passive RIS with NLOS in the direct link and passive RIS with LOS in the direct link. In both cases, the number of the reflecting units, N , is set to 2, 4, and 50. Regarding the number of CCI, which is M , that is affecting the destination terminal, BS, is set to 0, 1, and 2. The target rate is set to 10 bps/Hz in the performance analysis. The obtained results in Fig. 2 reveal that increasing the number of reflecting elements decreases the required transmit power. Results also reveal that the system model that contains LOS/direct-link achieves better OP, compared to its counterpart passive RIS with NLOS. However, it is also observed from Fig. 2 that the achieved LOS/direct-link coding gain effect becomes negligible when increasing the number of the reflecting elements in RIS. Lastly, CCI has a detrimental effects on the system outage performance for small number of reflecting elements while a large number of reflecting elements improves the communication performance under CCI, thus mitigating its effect on the system outage performance.

Fig. 3 shows the performance of the OP for two cases, i.e. active RIS with NLOS in the direct link and active RIS with LOS in the direct link. In both cases, the number of reflecting elements, N , is set to 2 and 50. The number of CCI, M is set to 0, 1, and 2 and the target rate is set to 10 bps/Hz. According to Fig. 3, increasing the number of CCI terminals causes system coding gain losses when the system has a low number of reflecting elements in both active RIS and active RIS with a direct link models. Since the CCI terminals are randomly deployed, Euclidean distance, d and the path-loss exponents, v , have a different impact in both modes. For instance, when $d = 10$ and $v = 3$ and also $M = 1, 2$, CCI causes slight coding gain losses compared to the case of the $M = 0$. However, when the $d = 10$ and $v = 2$ and also $M = 1, 2$, the CCI causes clear coding gain losses over the case of $M = 0$. It has to be stated that both modes

FIGURE 3. Outage probability analysis of active-RIS with NLOS and active-RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 50, M = 0, 1, 2, \rho = 1.1$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

FIGURE 4. Outage probability analysis of absorptive-RIS with NLOS and absorptive-RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 100, M = 0, 1, 2, \rho = 0.5$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

correspond to a similar outage performance under different number and values of the randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI terminals. On the other hand, increasing the number of reflecting elements, $N = 50$, enhances system stability and eliminates CCI effects for both modes. In addition, increasing the number of reflective elements eliminates the performance difference between the two modes. This demonstrates that communication through RIS is sufficient to achieve the same performance values when there are NLOS conditions between mobile users.

In addition, Fig. 4 depicts the OP performance analysis of absorptive RIS system with LOS/NLOS in the presence of non-orthogonal CCI at the destination. Since the absorptive RIS does not amplify the incident signal and also does not amplify the noise, it acts as a passive counterpart. Differently from the passive RIS, the absorptive RIS has a small amplification coefficient $\rho = 0.5$. Comparing Figs. 2 and 4,

FIGURE 7. Error probability analysis of absorptive-RIS with NLOS and absorptive-RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 12$ and $M = 0, 1, 2$.

FIGURE 8. Throughput performance analysis of Passive RIS with NLOS and passive RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 30, M = 0, 1, 2, \rho = 1$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

elements, the absorptive RIS achieves a similar performance with passive and active RIS in terms of minimizing the detrimental effect of the CCI and also enhancing the system coding gain. However, as it is mentioned earlier, to achieve these benefits, the number of reflecting elements in absorptive RIS needs to be twice compared to passive and active RIS. Results also reveal that system with LOS achieves a better EP, which is 20 dB, compared to NLOS for a small number of reflecting elements. However, this performance gain decreases by increasing the number of RIS elements.

Fig. 8 depicts the throughput performance analysis of passive RIS with NLOS and passive-RIS with LOS/direct-link system. Fig. 8 considers that number of reflecting element, N , is set to 2 and 30, and the number of CCI, M is set to 0,1,2, and the target rate, R_{th} is set to 10 bps/Hz. Since the CCI terminals are randomly deployed, two different Euclidean distances are considered, which are $d = 1, 10$, and the path-loss exponents are set to 2 and 3. In reference to Fig. 8, regardless of number

FIGURE 9. Throughput performance analysis of active RIS and active RIS with a direct-link for $N = 2, 30, M = 0, 1, 2, \rho = 1.1$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

of reflecting element, the system model that is operating via passive-RIS with LOS/direct-link achieves a better throughput performance than its counterpart passive-RIS with NLOS. The throughput performance difference between the models, LOS and NLOS, is prominent for RIS with low-reflecting elements, but diminishes to negligible levels as the number of reflecting elements increases. Fig. 8 also shows that for any mode, setting the CCI terminals' Euclidean distance to 1 and using only a low number of reflecting elements, $N = 2$, keeps the system throughput at very low levels across all SNR regimes. However, with a large number of reflecting elements, $N = 30$, the system's resistance to CCI improves, achieving performance similar to other configurations.

Then, Fig. 9 presents the throughput performance of system that is operating via active RIS with LOS/direct-link and active RIS with NLOS. Small and large number of reflecting elements, $N = 2, 30$, are considered for the throughput performance analysis. The target rate, R_{th} , is set to 10 bps/Hz and the number of randomly deployed CCI, M is set to 0,1, and 2. According to Fig. 9, the system that is operating with RIS with LOS/DL achieves a slightly better throughput performance compared to its counterpart RIS with NLOS model. The results also reveal that the performance gap mentioned earlier diminishes by increasing the number of reflecting elements to 30. As it is observed in the previous performance metrics, the d and v determine the severity of the detrimental effect of CCI. For example, setting $d = 10, v = 3$, and $M = 1, 2$, the CCI slightly causes coding gain losses on $M = 0$. Considering a similar setting and changing the v term to 2, the CCI causes more visible coding gain losses on $M = 0$ for both active RIS with LOS/direct-link and active RIS with NLOS modes. Moreover, regardless of the value of v , when d is set to 1, the performance curves tend to zero throughput along the whole range of SNR values. Nonetheless, by increasing the number of reflecting elements to 30, the system that operates in both modes becomes more stable and dominates the detrimental effect of the CCI, especially for $d = 1$ in both modes.

FIGURE 10. Throughput performance analysis of absorptive RIS with NLOS and absorptive RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 60$, $M = 0, 1, 2$, $\rho = 0.5$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

FIGURE 12. Energy Efficiency analysis of active RIS with NLOS and active RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 30$, $M = 0, 1, 2$, $P_s = 0, 1$ dBW, $\rho = 1.1$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

FIGURE 11. Energy Efficiency analysis of passive RIS with NLOS and passive RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 30$, $M = 0, 1, 2$, $P_s = 0, 1$ dBW, $\rho = 1$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

Next, Fig. 10 shows the throughput performance comparison of the system that is operating via absorptive RIS with NLOS and absorptive-RIS with LOS/direct-link. When compared to Figs. 8 and 9, the absorptive RIS with LOS/NLOS achieves slightly worse throughput performance than active and passive RIS with LOS/NLOS for a small number of RIS elements. By increasing the number of RIS elements, the absorptive RIS achieves a similar performance with its counterparts but requiring twice the number of reflecting elements.

In terms of EE, Fig. 11 presents corresponding results for passive RIS with NLOS and passive-RIS with LOS/direct-link system. The number of reflecting elements, N , is set to 2 and 30. The number of randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI terminal, M , is considered 0, 1, and 2. The target rate, R_{th} , is set to 10 bps/Hz. The Euclidean distance, d , is set to 1 and 10. The path-loss exponent, v , is set to 2 and 3 and the P_s is set to 0 and 1. According to Fig. 11, the system model with

LOS/direct-link achieves a better EE compared to its counterpart passive RIS with NLOS for small and large number of reflecting elements. In addition, $P_s = 0$ achieves a better EE compared to its counterpart $P_s = 1$. Results also reveal that regardless of the path-loss exponent and transmit power, $P_s = 0$ and 1, the Euclidean distance, $d = 1$, severely degrades the system EE and causes saturation along the SNR axis. However, increasing the number of reflecting elements to 30, the resistance of the system increases against the detrimental effects of the CCI. The results also show that a large number of reflecting elements eliminate the performance differences between the system models. Lastly, similar to the case with a small number of reflecting units, when a large number of reflecting units is considered, $P_s = 0$ achieves a better EE compared to $P_s = 1$.

Fig. 12 presents the EE analysis of active-RIS with NLOS and active-RIS with LOS/direct-link system. The number of reflecting element, N , is set to 2 and 30 and the number of randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI terminal, M , is considered 0, 1, and 2. As in the passive case, Fig. 11, the target rate, R_{th} , is set to 10 bps/Hz. and the Euclidean distance, d , is set to 1 and 10. In addition, the path-loss exponent, v , is set to 2 and 3 and the P_s is set to 0 and 1. In reference to Fig. 11, the system model with LOS/direct-link achieves a better EE compared to active RIS with NLOS system for a small and large number of reflecting elements. However, the aforementioned performance gap diminishes by increasing the number of reflecting elements. Moreover, $P_s = 0$ achieves a better EE compared to $P_s = 1$. Results also reveal that regardless of the path-loss exponent and transmit power, $P_s = 0$ and 1, the Euclidean distance, $d = 1$, severely degrades the system EE and causes saturation along the SNR axis for $N = 2$. Still, increasing the number of reflecting elements to 30, the resistance of the system increases against the detrimental effects of the CCI. As in the small reflecting unit, when the active RIS has a large number of reflecting units, $P_s = 0$ achieves a better EE compared to $P_s = 1$.

FIGURE 13. Energy Efficiency analysis of absorptive RIS with NLOS and absorptive RIS with LOS/direct-link for $N = 2, 60$, $M = 0, 1, 2$, $P_s = 0, 1$ dBW, $\rho = 0.5$, and $R_{th} = 10$ bps/Hz.

Finally, Fig. 13 presents the EE performance comparison of system that is operating with absorptive-RIS with NLOS and absorptive-RIS with LOS/direct-link. According to obtained results, comparing with the Figs. 11 and 12, it shows that the absorptive RIS achieves slightly worse EE performance than active and passive RIS for a small number of RIS elements. By increasing the number of RIS elements, the absorptive RIS with LOS/NLOS achieves a similar performance with its counterparts but with twice the number of reflecting elements.

V. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This work focused on the impact of randomly deployed CCI terminals, adopting NOMA-based communication, on a RIS-aided dual-hop network. More specifically, two different cases were presented, regarding the state of the direct link between the source and the destination. In the first case, communication takes place only via RIS while in the second case, a LOS direct link exists between the two terminals. Moreover, we also consider different RIS operation modes, i.e., active, passive, and absorptive and derive corresponding theoretical performance results. Here, we conducted performance evaluation for the outage and error probability, the throughput, and the energy and spectral efficiency. Results indicate that when a RIS with a low number of reflecting elements is deployed, the Euclidean distance and the path loss exponent have a greater impact on the effect of randomly deployed non-orthogonal CCI on the system performance than the number of CCI terminals affecting the destination terminal. However, when the RIS has a large number of reflecting elements, the system becomes stable, and CCI effects become negligible. In addition, it was shown that a system with RIS and LOS/direct-link achieves better performance, compared to the case with RIS and NLOS between the two terminals. Still, it was observed that the aforementioned performance gap becomes negligible

when the RIS has a large number of reflecting elements and thus the LOS/NLOS models achieve a similar performance.

Regarding the future directions of this study, the integration of NOMA-based RIS-aided communication in the uplink and downlink under CCI represents an interesting area [54], [55]. Also, considering additional practical scenarios, the investigation of the impact of imperfect channel state information on the system performance is of critical importance [56].

APPENDIX A PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1

Revisiting (2) and leveraging the logarithm and probability properties, following expressions are obtained

$$\begin{aligned}
 F\gamma_{BS}^{a+d}(\gamma) &= \Pr\left(\frac{P_s \left(|f| + \rho \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|\right)^2}{\Upsilon} \leq \underbrace{\gamma}_{2^{R_{th}-1}}\right) \\
 &= \Pr\left(\underbrace{\left(|f| + \rho \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|\right)}_A \leq \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s} \Upsilon\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right) \\
 &= F_A\left(\left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s} \Upsilon\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right), \tag{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\Upsilon = \rho^2 \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{n_i}^2 |g_i|^2 + \sum_{j=1}^M P_J \alpha_j |m_j|^2 + \sigma_{w_n}^2$. In order to continue the analysis, (22) requires the CDF of $A = \left(|f| + \rho \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|\right)$. In this regard, by defining the PDF of $\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|$, for the case $N > 1$, it is written as: $f_{\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|}(x) = \frac{x^a}{b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)} \exp\left(-\frac{x}{b}\right)$ [57, Eq. (6)], where $a = \frac{k_1^2}{k_2} - 1$ and $b = \frac{k_2}{k_1}$ [57, Eq. (7)], $k_1 = \frac{N\pi}{2}$ and $k_2 = 4N \left(1 - \frac{\pi^2}{16}\right)$ [57, Eq. (8)] and $F_{\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|}(x) = 1 - \frac{\Gamma(a+1, \frac{x}{b})}{\Gamma(a+1)}$ and $f_{|f|}(\gamma) = \frac{\gamma}{\Omega_f} e^{-\frac{\gamma^2}{2\Omega_f}}$ and $F_{|f|}(\gamma) = 1 - e^{-\frac{\gamma^2}{2\Omega_f}}$ [58]. By means of [59, Eq. (06.06.06.0001.02)], $F_{\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|}(x) = \left(\frac{x}{b}\right)^{a+1} / \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_A^{a+d}(\gamma) &= \Pr\left(\left(|f| + \rho \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|\right) \leq \gamma\right) \\
 &= \Pr\left(\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i| \leq \frac{\gamma - |f|}{\rho}\right) \\
 &= \int_0^\gamma F_{\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i||g_i|}\left(\frac{\gamma - |f|}{\rho}\right) f_{|f|}(x) dx. \tag{23}
 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the related CDF and PDF expressions into (23), following expression is obtained

$$\frac{1}{(\rho b)^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Omega_f} \underbrace{\int_0^\gamma x(\gamma-x)^{a+1} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\Omega_f}} dx}_I \tag{24}$$

By using [39, Eq. (3.478.3¹¹)], \mathcal{I} is solved as

$$\mathcal{I} = B(a+2, 2) \gamma^{a+3} {}_2F_2 \left(1, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a+4}{2}, \frac{a+5}{2}; \frac{-\gamma^2}{2\Omega_f} \right). \quad (25)$$

Note that $B(a+2, 2)$ in (25) is further simplified with the help of [39, Eq. (8.384.1)] as: $\frac{\Gamma(a+2)}{\Gamma(a+4)}$. Note that the i.i.d. scenario is considered for modeling the non-orthogonal CCIs. In this context, the sum of M i.i.d. Rayleigh distribution follows the Gamma distribution and its PDF is written as $f_{\gamma_F}(\gamma_F) = \left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^M \frac{\gamma_F^{M-1}}{(M-1)!} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}}$ [58], where $\gamma_F = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^M P_J |m_j|^2}{\sigma^2}$.

Likewise, $\gamma_G = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{n_i}^2 |g_i|^2}{\sigma^2}$ and its PDF is written as $f_{\gamma_G}(\gamma_G) = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}\right)^N \frac{\gamma_G^{N-1}}{(N-1)!} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}}$. Replacing the related SNR expression to (22), the following expression is obtained

$$F \gamma_{BS}^{a+d}(\gamma) = F_A \left(\left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s} (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right). \quad (26)$$

In this regard, substituting (24) and (25) into (26), the following integral expression is obtained.

$$F \gamma_{BS}^{a+d}(\gamma) = \frac{\Gamma(a+2)}{(\rho b)^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Omega_f \Gamma(a+4)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s} \right)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} \times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} {}_2F_2 \left(1, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a+4}{2}, \frac{a+5}{2}; \frac{-\gamma (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)}{2P_s \Omega_f} \right) f_{\gamma_G}(\gamma_G) f_{\gamma_F}(\gamma_F) d\gamma_G d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_1}. \quad (27)$$

Substituting the related PDF expressions into (27), \mathcal{I}_1 is written as

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g} \right)^N \left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m} \right)^M \frac{1}{\Gamma(M)\Gamma(N)} \times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} {}_2F_2 \left(1, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a+4}{2}, \frac{a+5}{2}; \frac{-\gamma (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)}{2P_s \Omega_f} \right) \gamma_G^{N-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}} \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_G d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_2}. \quad (28)$$

By means of [59, Eq. (07.25.06.0002.01)] and utilizing Pochhammer symbol, $(a)_n = \frac{\Gamma(a+n)}{\Gamma(a)}$ [39], \mathcal{I}_2 is further simplified as:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(1+k)\Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k)\Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2)\Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2P_s \Omega_f} \right)^k \times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+3}{2}+k}}_{\mathcal{I}_3}$$

$$\times \underbrace{\gamma_G^{N-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}} \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_G d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_3}. \quad (29)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (1.110)], \mathcal{I}_3 is further simplified as

$$\sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F)^u \times \underbrace{\gamma_G^{N-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}} \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_G d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_4}. \quad (30)$$

Note that since $(a+3+2k)/2$ is not integer in $\left(\frac{a+3+2k}{u}\right)$, $\binom{x}{y} = \frac{\Gamma(x+1)}{\Gamma(y+1)\Gamma(x-y+1)}$ [39] is utilized for the further simplification. By performing basic algebraic manipulations and using [39, Eq. (1.111)], \mathcal{I}_4 is further simplified as

$$\sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \int_0^\infty \gamma_G^{N+u-t-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}} d\gamma_G \times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \gamma_F^{M+t-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_5}. \quad (31)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (3.381.4)], the integral expressions in \mathcal{I}_5 are solved as

$$\mathcal{I}_5 = \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t)}{\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}\right)^{N+u-t}} \frac{\Gamma(M+t)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+t}}. \quad (32)$$

In summary, the final expression is obtained as in (5). Regarding passive RIS with LOS/direct-link analytical derivations, by setting the ρ term to 1 and also by setting the $\sigma_{n_i}^2$ term to zero in (22), following expression is obtained. Note that the term ρ is retained in the analysis because of the absorptive RIS.

$$F \gamma_{BS}^{p+d}(\gamma) = \frac{\Gamma(a+2)}{(\rho b)^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)\Omega_f \Gamma(a+4)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s} \right)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} \times \left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m} \right)^M \frac{1}{\Gamma(M)} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+3}{2}} {}_2F_2 \left(1, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a+4}{2}, \frac{a+5}{2}; \frac{-\gamma (\gamma_F + 1)}{2P_s \Omega_f} \right) \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_6}. \quad (33)$$

By means of [59, Eq. (07.25.06.0002.01)] and utilizing Pochhammer symbol, $(a)_n = \frac{\Gamma(a+n)}{\Gamma(a)}$ [39], \mathcal{I}_6 is further simplified as:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(1+k)\Gamma(3/2+k)}{\Gamma(3/2)} \frac{\Gamma((a+4)/2+k)\Gamma((a+5)/2+k)}{\Gamma((a+4)/2)\Gamma((a+5)/2)} k! \left(-\frac{\gamma}{2P_s \Omega_f} \right)^k$$

$$\times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty (\gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+3}{2}+k} \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_7}. \quad (34)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (1.110)], \mathcal{I}_7 is further simplified as

$$\sum_{u=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+2k+5}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+2k-2u+5}{2})} \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \gamma_F^{M+u-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_8}. \quad (35)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (3.381.4)], the integral expression in \mathcal{I}_8 is solved as

$$\mathcal{I}_8 = \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+u}}. \quad (36)$$

In summary, the final expression is obtained as in (6).

Regarding the system model that communicates via active RIS with NLOS, bypassing the direct link in (3), (22), and (23), the following expression is written

$$\begin{aligned} F_A^a(\gamma) &= \Pr\left(\rho \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i| |g_i| \leq \gamma\right) \\ &= \Pr\left(\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i| |g_i| \leq \frac{\gamma}{\rho}\right) \\ &= \int_0^\gamma F_{\sum_{i=1}^N |h_i| |g_i|}\left(\frac{\gamma}{\rho}\right) d\gamma \\ &= \frac{1}{b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1) \rho^a} \int_0^\gamma \gamma^a \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma}{\rho b}\right) d\gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (3.381.1)], (37) is solved as

$$\frac{\rho}{\Gamma(a+1)} \gamma \left(a+1, \frac{\gamma}{\rho b}\right). \quad (38)$$

By definition [60, Eq. (11)], (38) is obtained as:

$$F_A^a(\gamma) = \rho - \rho \frac{\Gamma(a+1, \frac{\gamma}{\rho b})}{\Gamma(a+1)}. \quad (39)$$

By means of [59, Eq. (06.06.06.0001.02)], $F_A^a(\gamma) = \rho \left(\frac{\gamma}{\rho b}\right)^{a+1} / \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)$. Utilizing the obtained results in (39), following expressions are obtained.

$$F \gamma_{BS}^a(\gamma) = F_A^a\left(\left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}(\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right). \quad (40)$$

In this regard, substituting the approximated (39) into (40), the following integral expression is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} F \gamma_{BS}^a(\gamma) &= \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} \\ &\times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} f_{\gamma_G}(\gamma_G) f_{\gamma_F}(\gamma_F) d\gamma_G d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_9}. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Substituting the related PDF expressions into (41), \mathcal{I}_9 is written as

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}\right)^N \left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^M \frac{1}{\Gamma(M)\Gamma(N)} \\ &\times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+1}{2}}}_{\mathcal{I}_{10}} \\ &\times \underbrace{\gamma_G^{N-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}} \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_G d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_{10}}. \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (1.110)], \mathcal{I}_{10} is further simplified as:

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{u=0}^\infty \frac{\Gamma(\frac{a+3}{2})}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(\frac{a+3-2u}{2})} \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty (\rho^2 \gamma_G + \gamma_F)^u}_{\mathcal{I}_{11}} \\ &\times \underbrace{\gamma_G^{N-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}} \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_G d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_{11}}. \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Note that since $(a+1)/2$ is not an integer in $\binom{x}{y} = \frac{\Gamma(x+1)}{\Gamma(y+1)\Gamma(x-y+1)}$ [39] is utilized for further simplification. By performing basic algebraic manipulations and using [39, Eq. (1.111)], \mathcal{I}_{11} is further simplified as

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{t=0}^u \binom{u}{t} \rho^{2(u-t)} \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \gamma_G^{N+u-t-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_G}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}} d\gamma_G}_{\mathcal{I}_{12}} \\ &\times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \gamma_F^{M+t-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_{12}}. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (3.381.4)], the integral expressions in \mathcal{I}_{12} are solved as

$$\mathcal{I}_{12} = \frac{\Gamma(N+u-t) \Gamma(M+t)}{\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_n^2 \Omega_g}\right)^{N+u-t} \left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+t}}. \quad (45)$$

In summary, the CDF expression of active-RIS with NLOS is presented in (8).

Regarding the passive RIS with NLOS counterpart, by setting the active RIS amplification coefficient to 1 in (37) and also eliminating the active-RIS component in (40), the following passive expression is obtained. Note that the term ρ is retained in the derivations for the absorptive counterpart.

$$F \gamma_{BS}^p(\gamma) = F_A^p\left(\left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}(\gamma_F + 1)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right), \quad (46)$$

Substituting the approximated (39), which is $F_A^p(\gamma) = \rho \left(\frac{\gamma}{\rho b}\right)^{a+1} / \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)$, into (46), the following expression is obtained

$$F \gamma_{BS}^p(\gamma) = \frac{1}{\rho^a b^{a+1} \Gamma(a+1)(a+1)} \left(\frac{\gamma}{P_s}\right)^{\frac{a+1}{2}}$$

$$\times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty (\gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} f_{\gamma_F}(\gamma_F) d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_{13}}. \quad (47)$$

Substituting the related PDF expressions into (47), \mathcal{I}_{13} is written as

$$\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^M \frac{1}{\Gamma(M)} \times \underbrace{\int_0^\infty (\gamma_F + 1)^{\frac{a+1}{2}} \gamma_F^{M-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_{14}}. \quad (48)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (1.110)], \mathcal{I}_{14} is further simplified as

$$\sum_{u=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{a+3}{2}\right)}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma\left(\frac{a+3-2u}{2}\right)} \underbrace{\int_0^\infty \gamma_F^{M+u-1} e^{-\frac{\gamma_F}{P_J \Omega_m}} d\gamma_F}_{\mathcal{I}_{15}}, \quad (49)$$

Since $(a+1)/2$ is not an integer in $\left(\frac{a+1}{u}\right)$, $\binom{x}{y} = \frac{\Gamma(x+1)}{\Gamma(y+1)\Gamma(x-y+1)}$ [39] is utilized for the further simplification. By means of [39, Eq. (3.381.4)], the integral expressions in \mathcal{I}_{15} are solved as

$$\mathcal{I}_{15} = \frac{\Gamma(M+u)}{\left(\frac{1}{P_J \Omega_m}\right)^{M+u}}. \quad (50)$$

APPENDIX B PROOF OF PROPOSITION 2

Starting with the active RIS when the source has a LOS link with the destination terminal, substituting the related CDF expression, (5), into EP formula, (9), following integral expression is obtained

$$\bar{P}_e^{a+d} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^\infty \gamma^{\frac{a+2k+2}{2}} \exp(-\gamma) d\gamma. \quad (51)$$

By means of [39, Eq. (3.381.4)], (51) is solved as: $\Gamma\left(\frac{a+2k+4}{2}\right)$. The final expression is written as in (10). Likewise, for passive RIS with LOS/direct-link, following a similar procedure and utilizing (6) and (9), and also solving the integral expression, $\Gamma\left(\frac{a+2k+4}{2}\right)$ is obtained. The final EP expression for passive RIS with LOS / direct-link is presented in (11).

Regarding the system model without a direct link for active and passive RIS modes, using (7) and (8) in (9) and also solving the integral expression with [39, Eq. (3.381.4)], the final EP expressions for the active and passive RIS-aided without a direct-link are obtained as in (12) and (13), respectively.

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